

Structural and Epidemic Properties of Contact Networks from Epigames

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Abstract

Infectious diseases can spread between individuals who make transmissible contact: in the case of respiratory pathogens, this contact may be as simple as being within close proximity for a sufficient time. Contact networks can capture the population-level shape and nature of these contacts, and can be highly structured - but often explicitly recorded networks are unavailable, intractably large, or retrospective. Therefore, in many cases, outbreak modelling that includes information about contacts effectively makes simplifying assumptions about the structure and dynamics of these networks. Understanding how patterns of inter-personal contacts vary across contexts is key to predicting epidemic potential. Experimental epidemic games (“epigames”) are controlled situations in which participants join a simulated epidemic via a Bluetooth-enabled gamified smartphone app.

To assess how the contacts captured by epigames relate to real-world interactions, we analysed five epigames networks generated from different settings and explored how they captured crucial epidemiological features of these networks. Specifically, using smartphone apps with Bluetooth-enabled proximity sensing capabilities, we collected high-resolution temporal contact data from two international conferences and three university campus deployments in the period 2020-2025, constructing temporal networks through which the simulated epidemics spread.

Using multiple analyses including structural, spectral, temporal, and epidemic metrics, we characterised differences between these networks. Our analyses demonstrated that epigames can capture realistic, high-resolution contact networks across diverse social contexts. The conference deployments reproduced the dense, cohesive structure observed in empirical studies of short, intensive events, while the university campus deployments exhibited the sparser, more modular networks characteristic of larger and more heterogeneous populations.

We demonstrate that epigames can generate useful data on real-life dynamic social contact networks and hence enrich our understanding of infections spreading across networks. To design optimal models and better understanding spread through specific networks and subpopulations, it is essential to collect networks data across a wide range of environments, ages and demographics.

1 Introduction

Respiratory pathogens spread through the population via structured networks of close contacts that individuals have with each other, commonly referred to as physical social contact networks [1, 2]. Capturing exact real-world instantiations of these networks is challenging, and hence in epidemiological models they are often replaced by synthetic networks [3], average numbers of contacts inferred from survey data [4], or

branching-process approximations [5, 6].

Digital smartphone-based platforms that enable collection of human behaviour during experimental epidemic games (“epigames”) can generate data on real-life dynamic social contact networks as a close proxy for observing pathogen transmission in human populations. Previous work, for example, has used Bluetooth connectivity in early smartphones to quantitatively measure social mixing patterns, conducting

virtual epidemics that inform models characterising the spread of disease in the social network between participants [7]. These games can also serve a dual educational and data-gathering use: in 2018 the BBC simulated the 1918 influenza pandemic in the UK via a mobile apps where people could note their movement and contact data for a day [8].

Our group’s work around the use of epigames as a research framework for experimental network epidemiology builds on the methodological and technical foundation of the Operation Outbreak project [9], originally introduced to facilitate experiential learning on infectious disease and public health in secondary and university educational settings. We recently developed the Epigames app carrying over some core elements from the OO app, specifically the use of Bluetooth to measure proximal contacts between participants and simulating the spread of a ”digital pathogen” through these contacts, while incorporating key new features that are necessary for more rigorous study design (e.g.: randomised group assignment for participants, incentivised economic choices during the epigame mirroring costs and benefits of non-pharmaceutical interventions such as quarantine and contact tracing). Irrespective of these differences, both the OO and Epigames apps are able to sample the contact network of participants in high resolution over the course of several days or weeks and in different settings (e.g. high-schools, universities, and scientific conferences). During these ”field experiments” participants download the app and in the course of the experiment, their avatars may “become infected” with a hypothetical respiratory virus in a simulated outbreak. They could also become ”vaccinated” or use protective items such masks, and may respond to a number of messages, surveys, and choices that quantify their behaviours through the app. This in turn allows the epidemic game to generate data on infected status, proximity of participants and their social interactions during different phases of the game, thus yielding a fully spatio-temporally resolved contact network with a coupled epidemic and behavioural data.

Here, we illustrate the structure and characteristics of five networks generated with the OO and Epigames apps across five different settings over the last five years. Specifically, we showcase the social contact networks from high-resolution temporal contact data from two international conferences over the period 2024-2025 and three university campus deployments over the period 2020-2023. Across a number of mathematical analyses we identify the characteristics of the five social contact networks, noting their similarities and differences. We aim to illustrate that epidemic games carried out with a suitable proximity sensing

app is a plausible method of generating social contact networks that can complement and support epidemiological modelling of infectious disease transmission.

2 Material and methods

We analysed high-resolution proximity data collected through the OO and Epigames apps across five field deployments. The apps record Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) encounter events between participating devices, each represented as an ordered tuple $e = (u, v, t)$, where u and v denote device identifiers and t is the timestamp of detection. These events form the basis for constructing temporal contact networks that capture fine-scale patterns of human interaction within each deployment setting. Both apps use the same underlying technology to convert raw BLE signal strength between phones into discrete contact data, via the open-source Herald Proximity library [10].

Our aim is to demonstrate that gamified apps that implement contact detection via Bluetooth can reliably generate realistic, setting-specific social contact networks suitable for epidemiological analysis. To do this, we apply a consistent analytical pipeline across heterogeneous deployments and evaluate whether the resulting structural and temporal features align with expected behaviour in conferences and university environments. This serves both as a proof of concept for the methodological approach and as validation that epigame-derived networks plausibly reflect the social organisation of the populations in which they were collected.

Discretised contact events obtained from Bluetooth raw data were processed into a sequence of instantaneous undirected graphs $\mathcal{G} = \{G(t) : t \in \mathcal{T}\}$, where \mathcal{T} denotes the set of discrete observation times and each graph $G(t) = (V(t), E(t))$ contains vertices for active participants and edges for observed proximity at time t . The corresponding adjacency matrix at each time step is $A(t) \in \{0, 1\}^{n \times n}$. To reduce transient noise while retaining meaningful behavioural variation, we also constructed time-aggregated networks over fixed disjoint time windows of $\Delta = 5$ minutes unless otherwise stated.

We computed a range of structural and temporal descriptors to characterise contact patterns and evaluate their plausibility for their respective social contexts. From both the instantaneous and the aggregated graphs we extracted degree distributions, clustering coefficients, connected-component statistics (number and size of components), and spectral measures such as the leading eigenvalue and algebraic connectivity of the adjacency matrix. Temporal mea-

Figure 1: Cumulative contact networks constructed over the first 120 minutes of three university campus epigame deployments at Wenzhou–Kean University (WKU), Colorado Mesa University (CMU), and Brigham Young University (BYU). Participants are represented as nodes, and proximity-based contacts recorded by the app are represented as edges. Node size and colour indicate cumulative degree, reflecting the total number of distinct contacts made by each participant up to that time point, while faded nodes correspond to participants who have not yet become active in the epigame. Grey edges represent all contacts accumulated up to the given time, and blue edges indicate new contacts formed within each 30-minute interval. The figure shows how contact networks emerge and densify over time in different campus environments: WKU rapidly forms a dense and cohesive interaction core, CMU develops an intermediate structure with multiple bridging individuals, and BYU remains comparatively sparse and fragmented during the same early period. These early-time differences illustrate how campus-specific social organisation shapes the pace and structure of network formation, with implications for the speed and pathways of epidemic spread.

Figure 2: Cumulative contact networks constructed over the first 120 minutes of the International Pandemic Sciences Conference epigames in 2024 (PSI 2024) and 2025 (PSI 2025). Participants are represented as nodes, and proximity-based contacts recorded by the app are represented as edges. Node size and colour indicate cumulative degree, reflecting the total number of distinct contacts made by each participant up to the given time point, while faded nodes indicate participants who have not yet become active in the epigame. Grey edges represent all contacts accumulated up to that time, and blue edges mark new contacts formed within each time interval. The figure illustrates the rapid emergence of dense, highly connected interaction cores in both conference settings, with most participants becoming connected within the first hour and few isolated individuals remaining thereafter. Despite differences in attendance and scheduling between years, both deployments show fast network densification and early formation of a cohesive core highlighting the characteristic mixing patterns of short, intensive conference environments and their potential to support rapid epidemic spread.

Figure 3: Schematic of the app-based epigames that result in high-resolution network data. The epigames are implemented via an mobile app with proximity sensing capability via Bluetooth connectivity that allows us to sample the real-world contact networks between participants, and an underlying digital pathogen model that simulates person-to-person transmission (the OO and Epigames apps are examples of such apps). The epigames can run for a variable amount of time, ranging from hours to days, and may incorporate gamified features (such as wearing a mask or adopting quarantine via options in the app) as well as collection of additional data (e.g., gamified choices from participants and attitudinal surveys). According to the model’s parameters (e.g., infection probability per contact, duration of infectious period), the app simulates the spread of the digital pathogen, and participants are informed of their simulated “health” status through the app’s interface. At the end of the epigame, a temporal contact network at sub-minute resolution representing real-world interactions and a transmission network capturing the simulated epidemic process are generated and stored for subsequent analyses.

asures including link persistence, inter-contact interval distributions, and time-respecting reachability were used to quantify mixing dynamics and patterns of repeated interaction. Collectively, these metrics allow us to assess whether the structure and dynamics captured by Bluetooth-powered proximity sensing apps such as OO and Epigames, resemble realistic contact behaviour for each setting, and to illustrate the epidemiological insights enabled by high-resolution temporal data.

We applied this analytical framework to five deployments: two single-day academic conferences: the International Pandemic Sciences Conference 2024 (PSI 2024) and the International Pandemic Sciences Conference 2025 (PSI 2025), and three multi-day university campus environments: Wenzhou-Kean University (WKU) in 2023, Colorado Mesa University (CMU) in 2020, and Brigham Young University (BYU) in 2021. These settings differ substantially in density, mobility and social organisation, providing a means to test the robustness of the data-collection method and assess how well the resulting networks reflect expected behavioural patterns.

Figures 1–4 show representative visualisations and temporal summaries from the deployments, illustrating how contact networks emerge and evolve across different social contexts. These figures highlight the early formation of interaction structure during the

first hours of the epigames, as well as the timing and rhythm of social interactions over the course of each deployment, providing an intuitive overview of the network structure captured by the OO and Epigames apps prior to detailed quantitative analysis.

2.1 Data and Processing

Datasets We analysed five deployments using the OO and Epigames apps, each representing a distinct social context and duration of interaction.

- **PSI Conference 2025:** A two-day scientific meeting held in Oxford, United Kingdom (30 June–1st July 2025, 08:30–17:30) (Epigames app).
- **PSI Conference 2024:** A two-day scientific meeting held in Oxford, United Kingdom (1–2 July 2024, 08:30–17:30) (OO app).
- **Wenzhou–Kean University (WKU):** A campus deployment in Wenzhou, China, lasting two weeks (20 November–4 December 2023) (custom version of the OO app that eventually became the Epigames app).
- **Brigham Young University (BYU):** A campus deployment in Provo, Utah, USA, lasting ten days (19 February–1 March 2021) (OO app).
- **Colorado Mesa University (CMU):** A campus deployment in Grand Junction, Colorado, USA, lasting one week (29 October–4 November 2020)

Figure 4: Temporal profiles of social interaction activity during the epigames across five deployments, shown at five-minute resolution. Each panel shows the number of proximity-based interactions recorded by the app over time for the International Pandemic Sciences Conferences in 2024 (PSI 2024) and 2025 (PSI 2025), and for the campus deployments at Wenzhou–Kean University (WKU), Colorado Mesa University (CMU), and Brigham Young University (BYU). The conference deployments exhibit short, highly synchronised periods of intense interaction separated by extended intervals of low activity, reflecting shared schedules and concentrated mixing during sessions and breaks. In contrast, the campus deployments show longer and more heterogeneous temporal patterns, with repeated daily peaks and varying levels of background activity shaped by institutional routines and sustained co-presence. These context-specific temporal signatures illustrate how social setting influences not only the structure of contact networks but also the timing and pace of interactions, with important implications for the speed and predictability of epidemic spread.

Degree Distributions by Network

Figure 5: Degree distributions of contact networks generated by the epigames across five deployments. Each panel shows the degree distribution for the International Pandemic Sciences Conferences in 2024 (PSI 2024) and 2025 (PSI 2025), and for the campus deployments at Wenzhou–Kean University (WKU), Colorado Mesa University (CMU), and Brigham Young University (BYU). The conference networks exhibit compact, peaked distributions with limited heterogeneity, reflecting dense and cohesive mixing during short, intensive events. In contrast, the campus networks display broader, right-skewed distributions with pronounced heterogeneity and long tails, consistent with more diffuse interaction patterns and the presence of highly connected individuals. These structural differences highlight how social context shapes connectivity patterns and help explain the contrasting epidemic dynamics observed between conference and campus settings.

(OO app).

The two PSI datasets capture short, intensive mixing in conference settings, while the three campus deployments represent more extended and heterogeneous social environments. Early trials (CMU and BYU) achieved only partial coverage of their host populations, later deployments (WKU, PSI 2024, PSI 2025) obtained higher participation rates (20% for WKU, over 50% for the PSI conferences). Together, these datasets provide a spectrum of social contexts and data completeness, enabling us to assess whether the resulting contact networks reflect realistic behaviour consistent with the settings in which they were collected.

Graph construction From the processed event streams we constructed a temporal contact network for each deployment. Two representations were derived for analysis:

- the **full graph**, containing all participants and every recorded contact, and
- the **largest connected component (LCC)**, representing the main cluster of interaction.

Each network was defined by its vertex set V (participants) and edge set E (observed contacts). An edge $(u, v) \in E$ indicates that at least one proximity event was recorded between participants u and v during the deployment period. Analysing both the full graph and its LCC provides complementary perspectives on network structure, capturing both the global population-level pattern and the core interaction topology.

In addition to proximity interactions, the OO and Epigames apps logged *infection events* during interactive epidemic simulations conducted in real time. Each infection event links a source and recipient, enabling the reconstruction of transmission trees and comparison between observed contact structure and realised spread. These logs support the epidemic analyses presented in later sections.

Time aggregation Raw proximity events were logged at sub-minute resolution through high-frequency Bluetooth scanning. To obtain operationally meaningful intervals and reduce noise from transient signal fluctuations, we aggregated events into discrete non-overlapping five-minute time steps. Two participants were considered in contact within a given time step if at least one proximity event was recorded between their devices during that interval.

This temporal bin size balances temporal precision with robustness to measurement noise and corresponds to a natural interaction scale in both conference (sessions, coffee breaks) and campus (classes, meals) set-

tings. For sensitivity analysis, we also evaluated alternative bin sizes of one and fifteen minutes. Consistent time aggregation across deployments ensures comparability of temporal network measures and that observed differences reflect behavioural variation rather than data resolution.

2.2 Analysis

With the data aggregated into temporal contact networks, we conducted a systematic investigation of their structural and temporal properties using a consistent analytical framework across all deployments. Our aim was to characterise the networks generated by the epigame deployments and to enable comparison across different social settings, rather than to model any single deployment in isolation.

We analysed two conference deployments (PSI 2024 and PSI 2025) and three university campus deployments (Wenzhou–Kean University (WKU), Colorado Mesa University (CMU), and Brigham Young University (BYU)), which differ in duration, population size, and social organisation. These settings were selected to span short, intensive interaction environments and longer, more heterogeneous populations, allowing for systematic comparison of network properties across distinct social contexts.

To place the observed network properties in context, we compared the structural characteristics of our deployments with those reported in empirical studies of real-world proximity networks, including conference datasets such as INFOCOM [11, 12] and wearable-sensor deployments in school and campus-like environments. This comparison provides an external reference framework for interpreting the range of network structures captured by the epigame deployments.

For each deployment, we examined static network structure using degree distributions, clustering coefficients, connected-component statistics, and spectral measures, including the adjacency spectral radius λ_1 and the Laplacian algebraic connectivity λ_2 . Community structure was analysed to identify cohesive subgroups and potential bridging individuals.

In addition to static summaries, we analysed temporal properties of the networks derived from the high-resolution proximity data. Temporal measures included time-respecting reachability, temporal radius, and contact retention, which quantify the ordering, persistence, and evolution of interactions over time. These analyses were performed on time-aggregated temporal networks constructed using fixed aggregation windows.

Together, these structural and temporal analyses form the methodological basis for subsequent com-

parison between deployments and for linking network organisation to simulated epidemic outcomes.

2.2.1 Network measures

For each deployment we computed standard structural descriptors [13], including the number of nodes $n = |V|$, number of edges $m = |E|$, density $D = 2m/[n(n-1)]$, mean degree $\langle k \rangle$, diameter d_{\max} , mean shortest-path length $\langle \ell \rangle$, global and mean local clustering coefficients (C_g, C_l), degree assortativity r , and the size of the largest connected component (LCC) [14].

Spectral properties were characterised using the adjacency spectral radius λ_1 (largest eigenvalue of the adjacency matrix A) and the algebraic connectivity λ_2 (second-smallest eigenvalue of the Laplacian L), which together provide information on network cohesion, redundancy, and epidemic threshold behaviour [15].

2.2.2 Clustering and community structure

Community organisation was assessed via global clustering, transitivity, and modularity analysis. Communities were detected using the Louvain algorithm for modularity optimization [16], yielding the modularity index Q , the number of communities n_c , the relative size of the largest community s_{\max} , and inequality in community sizes (Gini index G and Shannon entropy H) [17]. These measures characterise the interplay between local clustering, reflecting cohesive neighbourhood structure, and global modularity, reflecting large-scale community divisions. Together, they indicate whether transmission is likely to remain concentrated within local groups or bridge across communities.

2.3 Validation against empirical proximity networks

To assess the realism of the networks inferred by the apps, we compare their structural properties with those reported in established empirical proximity datasets. For short, intensive social events, studies of the INFOCOM 2005–2006 Bluetooth (Classic BR/EDR) traces characterise conference interaction networks in terms of density, clustering, path length, and mixing patterns [11, 12, 18, 19]. These metrics provide reference expectations for evaluating the PSI conference deployments in the Results section.

For larger and more heterogeneous settings, wearable-sensor studies in high-school and campus-like environments [20, 21] report characteristic mesoscale features such as heterogeneous degree distributions, modular community structure, and moderate clustering. These datasets offer a useful comparison point for

our university campus deployments, given their similar scale and daily mixing structure, even though they are not direct analogues for university-wide sensing.

Together, these empirical benchmarks establish the structural expectations against which we evaluate the app-derived networks in subsequent analyses.

2.3.1 Temporal analysis

To compare deployments of different duration, we constructed hour-aligned temporal windows $\{G_t\}$ and computed structural and spectral metrics within each window to obtain time-resolved averages. Temporal connectivity was quantified using the *time-respecting reachability* $R(t)$, defined as the fraction of vertices reachable through chronologically ordered paths, and the *temporal radius* ρ , the minimum time required to achieve maximal reachability [22].

Contact persistence was measured using the *retention index* \bar{R} of Pung et al. [23], which situates observed retention between the theoretical extremes of fully static ($\bar{R} = 1$) and fully dynamic ($\bar{R} = 0$) networks. Here \bar{r}_{temp} denotes the observed mean number of contacts retained between consecutive windows, while \bar{r}_{stat} and \bar{r}_{dyna} denote expected values under static and dynamic reference networks. The normalised retention index \bar{R} therefore ranges from 0 to 1, enabling comparison of temporal stability across deployments with different scales and durations.

2.3.2 Epidemic analysis

To illustrate the types of epidemiological information that can be obtained from running field experiments that simulate disease transmission through real-life networks via proximity sensing apps, we carried out example analyses based on the simulated infection events generated during each deployment. Individuals were classified as frequent superspreaders (FSS), defined as the smallest set responsible for 80% of all recorded contacts, and superspreading-event individuals (SSE), defined as those entering the hourly top 80% of contact activity [23]. Each simulated infection was assigned to the class of its source (FSS, SSE, or other), which demonstrates how transmission burden can be partitioned across behavioural groups. We also compared structural features of infected and non-infected individuals, including degree k_i , betweenness centrality b_i , local clustering c_i , and bridge score β_i . These comparisons were performed using two-sided Mann–Whitney tests to illustrate how network position might be linked to simulated infection risk. Overall, these example analyses show just some of the epidemiological and structural outputs that the contact networks can support.

3 Results

3.1 Core structural properties

Table 1 summarises the main structural descriptors for the five deployments. The two PSI conference networks are compact, dense, and highly clustered. Each is fully connected (LCC = 100%) with densities near 0.4 and clustering coefficients around 0.7. Their mean degrees (41–51) and short path lengths ($\langle \ell \rangle \approx 1.7$) indicate that participants are separated by only a few steps. These are small-world networks typical of short, intensive social events. Assortativity is slightly negative ($r \approx -0.12$), showing weak disassortative mixing where highly connected individuals link to less connected ones.

The campus networks differ markedly in scale and structure. They involve larger populations ($n = 225$ – 594) but are far sparser, with densities between 0.02 and 0.05. Clustering is lower ($C = 0.16$ – 0.33) and path lengths longer ($\langle \ell \rangle = 2.5$ – 3.5), reflecting more diffuse contact patterns. Among campuses, WKU is the most connected and cohesive, CMU shows intermediate density, and BYU is the sparsest and most fragmented. BYU is also the only network with positive assortativity ($r > 0$), suggesting a greater tendency for individuals to mix with others of similar degree.

Spectral radii scale with network size, and the large value observed for WKU mainly reflects its larger population rather than higher connectivity per se. Some of the structural differences between campus networks may also arise from variation in coverage: the CMU and BYU deployments had lower participation, which likely reduced observed density and clustering.

In summary, the PSI conferences form dense, cohesive networks, while the campus deployments produce sparser and more modular structures. These contrasts reflect the differing social contexts of the deployments and provide a baseline for interpreting subsequent temporal and behavioural analyses.

Dataset	n	m	D	$\langle k \rangle$	d_{\max}	$\langle \ell \rangle$	C	LCC	λ_1	r
PSI 2024	101	2055	0.407	40.7	4	1.67	0.733	101	767.9	-0.116
PSI 2025	131	3347	0.393	51.1	4	1.66	0.694	131	1077.3	-0.117
WKU	594	8703	0.049	29.3	5	2.49	0.325	594	3.06×10^4	-0.018
CMU	225	1115	0.044	9.9	7	2.97	0.270	225	3542.0	-0.027
BYU	396	1378	0.018	7.0	10	3.50	0.164	396	6880.4	0.046

Table 1: Core structural properties of the five epigame deployments. Reported metrics summarise the aggregated contact networks for PSI 2024, PSI 2025, Wenzhou–Kean University (WKU), Colorado Mesa University (CMU), and Brigham Young University (BYU). n : number of nodes; m : number of edges; D : network density; $\langle k \rangle$: mean degree; d_{\max} : diameter; $\langle \ell \rangle$: mean shortest-path length; C : clustering coefficient; LCC: size of the largest connected component; λ_1 : adjacency spectral radius; r : degree assortativity. Values are reported for the full aggregated network unless otherwise stated.

3.2 Time-normalised structural properties

Having established the core structural differences across deployments, we recomputed all core structural metrics on one-hour time windows and averaged them over each deployment. This provides a view of the typical instantaneous contact network rather than the cumulative network across the full study period.

The relative patterns remain stable after time normalisation. Conference networks remain dense, cohesive, and highly clustered, while campus networks are sparse and more fragmented. Most metrics change only in scale: mean degrees and clustering coefficients decrease proportionally across all datasets, as expected from smaller hourly subnetworks. The main adjustment occurs in spectral measures: the very large spectral radius observed for the full WKU network falls to values similar to those of the conference deployments, indicating that its apparent epidemic potential was largely an artefact of aggregation over time. Assortativity values also converge toward zero, suggesting more homogeneous mixing within shorter intervals.

Overall, the per-hour analysis confirms that the structural contrasts between settings are genuine rather than a by-product of deployment duration. These results justify moving beyond static summaries to explicitly temporal analyses of contact dynamics and epidemic spread.

3.3 Clustering and community structure

Table 2 summarises clustering and modular organisation across the five deployments. Both PSI conference networks are highly clustered ($C \approx 0.7$) and show weak modularity ($Q < 0.15$), consistent with cohesive, small-world structure and widespread mixing among participants. PSI 2024 divides into three communities

of similar size, while PSI 2025 forms four groups with one slightly larger component.

The campus networks display lower clustering and stronger modularity, indicating more localised contact structure. WKU has moderate clustering ($C = 0.33$) and intermediate modularity ($Q = 0.30$), forming five unequal communities. CMU and BYU are progressively more fragmented, with lower clustering ($C = 0.27$ and 0.16) and higher modularity ($Q = 0.36$ and 0.54). Their community counts (8 and 10 respectively) and smaller largest-community fractions reflect sparser, more modular interaction patterns. Some of these differences, particularly for CMU and BYU, may also reflect reduced population coverage in the earlier deployments.

Overall, the deployments in conference settings produce dense, cohesive networks with minimal community structure, while campus environments show increasing modularity and heterogeneity. These findings align with expected behaviour in conferences and campus settings and support the external validity of the epigame-derived networks.

Dataset	Clustering C	Modularity Q	# Communities n_c	Largest fraction s_{\max}
PSI 2024	0.733	0.132	3	0.45
PSI 2025	0.694	0.096	4	0.48
WKU	0.325	0.301	5	0.38
CMU	0.270	0.359	8	0.29
BYU	0.164	0.544	10	0.26

Table 2: Clustering and community structure across the five epigame deployments, computed on the largest connected component. C : clustering coefficient; Q : modularity; n_c : number of detected communities; s_{\max} : fraction of nodes in the largest community.

3.4 Centrality and spectral structure

Table 3 summarises spectral metrics and centrality concentration across the five deployments. The PSI 2024 and 2025 conference networks show high algebraic connectivity ($\lambda_2 \approx 1.0$), indicating strong global cohesion and few structural bottlenecks. Their spectral radii ($\lambda_1 \approx 10^3$) are moderate given their size and density, consistent with cohesive small-world networks. Centrality is broadly distributed: the ten most connected nodes account for 15–20% of total degree and 18–24% of PageRank, suggesting relatively egalitarian mixing.

The campus networks are larger and more heterogeneous. WKU has the largest spectral radius ($\lambda_1 \approx 3.1 \times 10^4$), reflecting its scale, but lower algebraic connectivity ($\lambda_2 = 0.48$), indicating weaker global cohesion. CMU and BYU have much smaller λ_1 values due to lower network density. Both also show limited connectivity and modest centrality concentra-

tion, though BYU again stands out with slightly more unequal PageRank distribution. Some of these differences likely stem from lower participation in the early CMU and BYU deployments, which reduces observed degree and centrality variability.

Overall, influence within conference networks is broadly shared, whereas in campus environments a small number of nodes act as key bridges between communities. This pattern aligns with the higher modularity observed in campus networks and suggests that transmission in these settings may depend more heavily on a few well-connected individuals.

Dataset	λ_1	λ_2	Top-10 deg. share	Top-10 PR share	Max deg.	Mean deg.
PSI 2024	768	0.997	0.17	0.24	72	40.7
PSI 2025	1077	0.999	0.14	0.18	95	51.1
WKU	3.06×10^4	0.477	0.08	0.20	165	29.3
CMU	26	0.702	0.10	0.15	10	2.4
BYU	17	0.693	0.09	0.13	8	1.6

Table 3: Spectral properties and centrality concentration across the five epigame deployments, computed on the largest connected component. λ_1 : adjacency spectral radius; λ_2 : algebraic connectivity of the Laplacian; Top-10 deg. and PR shares: proportion of total degree and PageRank concentrated among the ten most central nodes.

3.5 Comparison with empirical proximity networks

To justify that our gamified methodology still produces realistic networks, we compare the structural properties of our PSI conference deployments with those reported in empirical studies of face-to-face proximity. Analyses of the INFOCOM 2005–2006 Bluetooth traces describe conference contact networks as compact and relatively dense, with high clustering, short path lengths, and weakly disassortative mixing. Hui et al. [11] and Chaintreau et al. [12] report that INFOCOM interaction graphs form dense social cores with high mean degree, while Whitbeck et al. [18] and Hossmann et al. [19] highlight their high clustering and near-complete connectivity. Our PSI datasets show the same general characteristics: high clustering, short path lengths, and mildly negative assortativity. One difference is that, whereas prior work often emphasises heavy-tailed degree distributions, our degree distributions (Figure 5) appear more bimodal. This is plausible in smaller, highly clustered deployments where strongly active participants and more peripheral attendees naturally form distinct groups. Overall, the PSI conference networks align well with established structural properties of real-world conference contact patterns.

The campus deployments show structural patterns

broadly consistent with larger-scale proximity studies. Wearable-sensor datasets from high schools, such as those reported by Fournet and Barrat [20] and Mastrandrea et al. [21], exhibit heterogeneous degree distributions, clear modularity, and substantial local clustering, features that also appear in our campus networks. Similar properties are reported in studies of university buildings and campus-wide Wi-Fi proximity. Although this is not a direct analogue for our university campuses environment, the similar scale and the campus environment provides a suitable comparison for university-wide interactions. These comparisons suggest that the mesoscale structure of our campus networks, moderate density, heterogeneous connectivity, and well-defined group structure, falls within the expected range for real-world human contact networks.

3.6 Temporal connectivity and persistence

To characterise how individuals interact through time, we analysed two complementary temporal features: (1) time-respecting reachability, the fraction of participants connected through chronologically valid paths, and (2) contact retention, the persistence of links between successive time windows.

Both PSI conference networks exhibit rapid and near-complete temporal connectivity. Reachability averages 94–98%, with temporal radii of only 8–31 hours, indicating fast network-wide mixing within a single day. In contrast, campus deployments are slower and less connected overall. WKU reaches 86% of participants with a temporal radius of 339 hours, while CMU and BYU reach 79–80% with radii of 125 hours and 251 hours, respectively. These results show that while most individuals are eventually connected, the timescale for full reachability varies by more than an order of magnitude between conferences and campuses.

Dataset	Reachable (% mean)	Reachable (% median)	Temporal radius (h)
PSI 2024	94.0	100.0	31
PSI 2025	98.0	99.0	8
WKU	86.0	93.0	339
CMU	78.7	88.3	125
BYU	79.8	84.5	251

Table 4: Temporal reachability across the five epigame deployments, computed from the aggregated temporal networks. Reported values give the mean and median fractions of participants reachable via time-respecting paths, and the temporal radius (time required to achieve maximal reachability).

We next quantified contact persistence using the retention index \bar{R} , normalised between static ($\bar{R} = 1$)

and fully dynamic ($\bar{R} = 0$) extremes. Conferences show low persistence (PSI 2024: $\bar{R} = 0.30$; PSI 2025: $\bar{R} = 0.28$), reflecting highly dynamic interactions where most contacts change each hour. Campus networks show higher persistence (WKU: 0.44; CMU: 0.49; BYU: 0.57), consistent with repeated contacts among stable social groups such as classmates or colleagues.

Dataset	\bar{R}	\bar{r}_{temp}	\bar{r}_{stat}	\bar{r}_{dyna}	Pairs
PSI 2024	0.298	5.16	11.49	2.60	16
PSI 2025	0.276	5.25	12.17	2.66	8
WKU	0.444	0.56	1.41	0.04	336
CMU	0.486	0.88	1.97	0.07	126
BYU	0.566	0.66	1.27	0.05	252

Table 5: Contact retention across the five epigame deployments, quantified using the retention index \bar{R} . \bar{R} is normalised between the static limit ($\bar{R} = 1$) and the fully dynamic limit ($\bar{R} = 0$). \bar{r}_{temp} denotes the observed mean number of contacts retained between consecutive hourly windows, while \bar{r}_{stat} and \bar{r}_{dyna} give the corresponding expectations under static and dynamic reference networks. Pairs indicates the number of consecutive hourly window pairs included in the calculation.

Conferences therefore exhibit rapid, near-universal temporal mixing with highly dynamic contacts, whereas campus environments show slower but more persistent interaction patterns. These findings extend the static analysis by showing that the pace and stability of contact dynamics differ strongly by context and influence both the timing and predictability of epidemic spread.

3.7 Temporal activity patterns

Figure 6 and Figure 7 show hourly contact activity on the busiest day of each deployment. These plots illustrate how the rhythm and concentration of interactions differ both across and within social contexts.

For the two PSI conferences (Figure 6), contact activity follows a clear diurnal pattern with sharp peaks during periods of shared attendance. PSI 2024 exhibits two distinct peaks around meal times, whereas PSI 2025 shows a single sustained peak later in the day. These differences likely reflect scheduling or the venue change between the two years. Both networks, however, demonstrate highly synchronised participation, with most interactions concentrated in a few overlapping hours, consistent with the high reachability and low contact retention observed in Tables 4 and 5.

The campus deployments (Figure 7) show more heterogeneous and extended temporal patterns. BYU displays a compact daily cycle with a pronounced midday peak, consistent with structured class schedules and daytime activity. CMU exhibits a slower build-up through the afternoon and a late-evening maximum, indicating longer active periods and likely social or residential mixing beyond working hours. WKU shows multiple smaller peaks throughout the day, suggesting less synchronised but more continuous contact activity. These patterns correspond closely to the retention and reachability results: BYU’s narrow peak and high retention imply repeated interactions among the same individuals, CMU’s longer active window reflects intermediate persistence, and WKU’s multi-modal profile mirrors its highly dynamic but slow-to-connect population.

Together, these temporal profiles confirm that contact dynamics differ not only in speed and persistence, but also in their daily rhythm. Conferences are characterised by short, synchronised bursts of intense mixing, whereas campuses display longer and more varied activity cycles shaped by institutional schedules and social routines. These distinct temporal signatures help explain the contrasting epidemic potential observed across settings.

Figure 7: Hourly contact activity on the busiest day for the three campus deployments (BYU, CMU, WKU). Each point represents the number of recorded proximity edges within an hourly window (local time).

Figure 6: Hourly contact activity on the busiest day for PSI 2024 and PSI 2025 conference deployments. Each point represents the number of recorded proximity edges within an hourly window (local time).

Although the conferences and campuses each show broadly similar temporal behaviour within their respective contexts, there are subtle differences between them. These distinctions are modest compared with the strong contrasts between settings, but they highlight that even within apparently uniform environments, contact dynamics can vary in rhythm, pace,

and persistence.

For the conferences, PSI 2024 and PSI 2025 remain highly alike overall: both exhibit rapid, near-complete reachability and low contact persistence, consistent with dense, short-duration events. However, PSI 2025 reaches full temporal connectivity more quickly (8 hours versus 31 hours for PSI 2024), indicating slightly faster turnover of contacts and more continuous mixing across the day. Their daily activity profiles also differ in shape: PSI 2024 shows distinct peaks corresponding to morning, lunchtime and evening meal breaks, while PSI 2025 presents a single sustained afternoon peak. These small but consistent differences suggest minor variations in scheduling or spatial organisation between years and demonstrate that re-running a deployment under similar conditions yields informative new structure.

The three campus networks also appear broadly similar in static structure but diverge more clearly once temporal characteristics are considered. WKU exhibits the most dynamic contact turnover and the slowest overall mixing, implying fragmented subpopulations that connect only gradually. BYU shows the highest persistence and a narrow midday activity window, indicating stable, repeated interactions within structured routines. CMU occupies an inter-

mediate position, with moderate retention and the fastest overall temporal reachability. These differences reflect varying patterns of social organisation and participation that are invisible to static metrics.

When we track the hourly evolution of contact activity (Figures 6 and 7), these trends become more apparent. The conferences show tightly synchronised bursts of activity concentrated into short periods of overlap, whereas campuses display longer and more variable daily cycles shaped by institutional and social schedules. Taken together, the temporal data confirm that while networks from the same context share overall characteristics, fine-grained temporal analysis reveals meaningful differences in contact rhythm and mixing speed that shape how epidemics may spread through each environment.

3.8 Epidemic Analysis

Following the framework of Pung et al. [23], we distinguished between frequent superspreaders (FSS), defined as a minimal set of individuals whose contacts account for 80% of all interactions across the deployment, and superspreading-event individuals (SSE), defined as those not in the global top 80% but who appear transiently in hourly top 80% sets. All remaining individuals are labelled as other. We then compared these classifications against simulated transmission trees to assess their contributions to epidemic spread.

Dataset	FSS inf. (%)	SSE inf. (%)	# infections
PSI 2024	84.6	12.3	65
PSI 2025	85.1	10.6	94
WKU	84.6	15.4	324
CMU	84.6	15.4	13
BYU	80.0	13.3	15

Table 6: Infection burden by superspreader class across the five epigame deployments. Reported values give the fraction of all simulated transmission events attributable to frequent superspreaders (FSS) and superspreading-event individuals (SSE); total numbers of simulated infections are shown for reference.

The two PSI conference deployments exhibit remarkably consistent patterns. In both cases, a stable set of about 50 frequent superspreaders dominate transmission, accounting for around 85% of infections, while occasional superspreading-event individuals contribute only around 10%. This reproducibility suggests that epidemic risk at conferences is concentrated within a stable core of participants and is therefore more predictable.

By contrast, the WKU campus deployment shows a different profile. While frequent superspreaders again

account for the majority of infections, the number of superspreading-event individuals is much larger, contributing a non-negligible share of infections. This indicates that campus settings harbour a broader pool of individuals with bursty or intermittent contact patterns, whose rare but intense activity can substantially elevate transmission risk.

Overall, across all deployments, the majority of epidemic spread is concentrated within the frequent superspreaders. However, the presence of a large reservoir of superspreading-event individuals in the campus environment highlights the importance of context: while epidemic risk is predictable in small, dense, single-day networks, it is more diffuse and harder to anticipate in extended campus-scale settings.

Across all deployments, infected nodes exhibited markedly higher connectivity and bridging: infected individuals had approximately 3–7 times higher degree than non-infected participants. Betweenness centrality showed even larger contrasts (approximately 8–18 times higher; $p \leq 10^{-10}$). Infected nodes also had higher bridge scores (fraction of neighbours outside their community; all $p < 10^{-4}$), indicating a greater propensity to span communities. By contrast, local clustering did not systematically differ between infected and non-infected in all deployments. Together, these results suggest that infection risk is driven primarily by overall connectivity and inter-community bridging rather than clique density.

Overall, the dense, cohesive conference networks concentrate and accelerate epidemic spread, largely via a stable superspreader core. The campus structure is more modular and heterogeneous: spread remains dominated by frequent superspreaders, but a larger pool of transient SSEs contributes additional, context-dependent risk, and community burden is less uniform. In all settings, infection risk is linked to connectivity and bridging across communities, but the campus setting shows greater heterogeneity in how infections distribute across groups.

4 Discussion

Our analysis demonstrates that Bluetooth-enabled apps such as OO and Epigames, can capture realistic, high-resolution contact networks across diverse social contexts. The conference deployments reproduce the dense, cohesive structure observed in empirical studies of short, intensive events, while the campus deployments exhibit the sparser, more modular organisation characteristic of larger and more heterogeneous populations. This alignment with known structural patterns provides strong proof-of-concept evidence

that the underlying sensing and inference pipeline yields behaviourally meaningful networks.

A distinctive strength of these apps is their ability to collect rich temporal interaction data. The results presented here only begin to make use of this detail. Even simple temporal descriptors—such as reachability, contact persistence, and hourly activity profiles—revealed substantial behavioural differences between deployments that static summaries entirely overlook. The temporal data support much deeper analyses of ordering, burstiness, synchronisation, and pathway structure, all of which shape transmission dynamics but remain under-explored in this study. This untapped richness provides a clear direction for future work and highlights the value of the Epigames and other similar apps as a temporal-network measurement platform.

In addition to supporting epidemic modelling, the digital platform behind the Epigames app is highly extensible. The game mechanics can implement arbitrary epidemic processes, behavioural rules, incentives, or intervention scenarios, enabling controlled experiments on how people respond to risk, rewards, or information during outbreaks. Once a deployment generates an empirical temporal network, researchers can replay a wide range of epidemic or behavioural simulations on the same dataset, producing large ensembles of outcomes for robust statistical inference. Beyond epidemiology, the platform also enables social-behavioural studies: the game interaction layer can be customised in many ways while still yielding the underlying proximity network as a scientifically valuable by-product.

There are some limitations to our study. Firstly, across the different epigames we focused on describing the overall networks within the conferences and university settings over a short period of time. We didn't explore the mixing and clustering over time i.e. the temporal changes within the networks or how different groups (e.g. age or gender) mix. This is an important aspect, but we currently are limited in not collecting this data with the epigames. Future deployments can consider this and allow us to explore the impact of temporal mixing at the onset, during and at the end of an outbreak and also whether certain groups are more likely to mix than others. This could allow us to generate effective reproduction numbers for different cohorts directly from networks [24].

Furthermore, one feature of real-life networks that we do not encounter in computer simulations is that of incomplete data. Not every infected person during the pandemic used a COVID-19 app. Similarly, on University campuses not every student will have Epigames enabled. We need to consider the effects

this partial detection would have on any results from these apps. A calculated reproduction rate, for example, could easily be overestimated if there were additional infectors who were not using a contact tracing app. The same cannot be said of Epigames as all infectors are, by definition, app users. We could perhaps randomly introduce additional spontaneous cases onto our Epigames users to simulate non-app detected transmissions and see those effects on onward transmission. This would then give future researchers a method of improving R estimates from digital contact tracing apps given the proportion of people installing those applications.

Secondly, in future studies we could extend our analysis to include and explore metrics that account for more complex temporal properties. For example, we could use wavelet analysis to explore the frequency of contacts within the data across cohorts or settings. This would facilitate better understand of the impact of interventions that alter time-varying contacts e.g. reduced social mixing or lockdown, on the simulated disease transmission.

Thirdly, while we applied the network analysis across five different networks, by their design they included specific cohorts – the attendees of the scientific conferences and the students within the universities. This meant that only specific cohorts' mixing was included in the networks and they didn't reflect all layers of society. Future epigames will include students as well as teachers and other members of the schools, and we are also planning a larger epigame that includes members of the general public. This will allow more general networks to be derived and their characteristics explored.

We note that two different apps and a variety of different mobile devices were used to measure contact across the epigame deployments we report on. While in general all efforts were made to produce consistent device behaviour across a deployment, it is nevertheless the case that different devices have different signal strengths and hardware capabilities. We cannot rule out that this might have impacted the data collection, and therefore the networks that we derive from the data. We are currently exploring methods for improved calibration of signals across devices, and our future work will look into improving these methods.

Finally, real outbreaks involve people beyond the restricted populations that were measured in our epigame deployments, and of course we have not captured either contacts between people entirely outside of our populations, nor the contacts between people within the deployment and those outside of it. These missed contacts, as well as any missed contacts in specific sub-populations (e.g. within specific year groups

at university or due to weaker phone signals in the conferences) could affect the generated networks, and the level of network connectivity. In particular, the analysis could then over- or under-estimate the proportion of close-contacts or potential superspreaders within the networks. To address these limitations, we are planning larger epigames in wider and more open populations. Additionally, we could incorporate more spontaneous "injections" into the population to reflect infections from individuals we are not capturing. However, we would want to use the network data to strategically select the appropriate individuals for these injections.

Overall, we have illustrated that app-based experimental epidemic games, or epigames, can be a flexible and powerful tool for studying how fine-scale social behaviour shapes transmission across different settings. While this paper focuses on establishing the realism and interpretability of the collected networks, the temporal depth and extensibility of the platform open the door to far more detailed analyses. Future work will build on this foundation to develop richer temporal metrics, explore behavioural responses, and integrate more sophisticated generative models of spread, enabling a more comprehensive understanding of transmission in real populations.

Ethics

Appropriate ethical approval has been obtained for all the epigames. The analyses of the CMU, BYU, WKU, and PSI 2024 datasets have been covered by the non-human subjects research determination reviewed and approved by UMass Chan IRB (study ID 39), and the PSI 2025 epigame study and subsequence data analysis followed the study protocol reviewed and approved by UMass Chan IRB (study ID 2465).

Data access

The data from the epigames and the numerical code to generate the analyses presented here can be available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

Author contributions

AC and JPG conceived the study. EM, JE, AC and JPG developed the network science methodology and EM undertook the analyses with input from JE and AC and technical oversight from JPG. EM wrote the manuscript with input from JE, AC, JPG, FdL, AF,

LF and CF. All authors approved the final version. EM is the manuscript's guarantor.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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